

ISSN: 2181-4066

DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4066

VOLUME I, ISSUE 9

JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ**

IMFAKTOR

SEPTEMBER | 2023

ISSN: 2181-4066
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4066

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

I-ЖИЛД, 9-СОҢ

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-9

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-9

ТОШКЕНТ - 2023

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

№ 9 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.56017/2181-4066-2023-9>

Бош муҳаррир:

Нишонова З.

– психология фанлари доктори, профессор

Масъул муҳаррир:

Давлатов О. Ғ.

– педагогика фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори

Таҳририят аъзолари:

1. Юсупова Хабиба Ирискуловна – педагогика ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
2. Олимов Лазиз Ярашович – психология ф.б.ф.д. (PhD), доцент
3. Элов Зиёдулло Сатторович – психология ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
4. Ганжиев Феруз Фурқатович – психология ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
5. Мусаева Мухаббат Эшбаевна – педагогика ф.б.ф.д. (PhD), доцент
6. Умаров Баҳром Норбоевич – педагогика ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
7. Орипова Раънохон Иброхимовна – педагогика фанлари номзоди, доцент
8. Ўринова Феруза Ўлжаевна – педагогика фанлари номзоди, доцент
9. Ниёзова Лутфия Худайбергановна – дефектолог - эксперт
10. Салиева Дилором Абдуллаевна – психология фанлари номзоди
11. Останов Шухрат Шарифович – психология ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
12. Рустамов Шавкат Шухратович – психология ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
13. Халлокова Максудахон Эргашевна – педагогика ф.б.ф.д. (PhD)
14. Исмайлова Раъно Нураевна – психология ф.б.ф.д. (PhD), доцент

“Педагогик ва психологик тадқиқотлар” журнали 2022 йил 22 декабрь куни № 054834-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Мазкур журнал 6 та халқаро маълумотлар базаларида индексланган бўлиб, жорий йил учун **UIF 2023 = 8.2 “импакт-фактор”** кўрсаткичига эга.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий таълим, фан ва инновациялар вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Олий аттестация комиссиясининг 2023 йил 24 июлдаги 01-02/1199-сонли хатига мувофиқ ушбу журналда чоп этилган мақолалар **хорижий мақолалар сифатида тан олинади.**

Саҳифаловчи\Page Maker\Верстка: Абдураҳмон Хасанов

Таҳририят манзили: Тошкент шаҳар, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2/27-уй. Почта индекси 100152. Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz/com

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55, E-mail: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

© “ИМФАКТОР Pages” илмий нашриёти, 2023 йил.

© Муаллифлар жамоаси, 2023 йил.

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

KOMOLOVA Gulhayo Shukirillo qizi

PhD student of Andijan

Mechanical Engineering Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8356123>

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER TECHNICAL EDUCATION

ANNOTATION

In this article, the role of pedagogical technologies in teaching mathematics in the higher technical education system and the importance of improving the pedagogical system, the successful application of pedagogical technologies to the educational process and the formation of a holistic view of the content of science, the main issues of using the elements of pedagogical technology that ensure coherence and the level of solving them is given.

Key words: higher, technical education, mathematics, pedagogical technologies, technologies.

OLIVY TEXNIK TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MATEMATIKA O'QITISHNING PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR ROLI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada oliy texnik ta'lim tizimida matematika o'qitishning pedagogik texnologiyalar roli va pedagogik tizimni takomillashtirish, pedagogik texnologiyalarni ta'lim jarayoniga muvaffaqiyatli tadbiq etish va fan mazmuniga yaxlit qarashni shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati, uzviylikni ta'minlovchi pedagogik texnologiya elementlarini qo'llashning asosiy masalalari va ularni xal kilish darajasi berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy, texnik ta'lim, matematika, pedagogik texnologiyalar, texnologiyalar.

РОЛЬ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ МАТЕМАТИКИ В СИСТЕМЕ ВЫСШЕГО ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается роль педагогических технологий в преподавании математики в системе высшего технического образования и важность совершенствования педагогической системы, успешного применения педагогических технологий в образовательном процессе и формирования целостного представления о содержании науки. Приведены основные вопросы использования элементов педагогической технологии, обеспечивающих связность, и уровень их решения.

Ключевые слова: высшее, техническое образование, математика, педагогические технологии, технологии.

At the modern stage of scientific and technical development, special attention is paid to the promotion of mathematical knowledge. After all, mathematics is the theoretical basis of all scientific sciences and the practical basis of production in various fields. Therefore, development of students' mathematical abilities is one of the most important tasks of modern education.

There are also different opinions about the application of pedagogical technologies to the educational process. For example, in order to improve the pedagogical system and successfully apply pedagogical technologies to the educational process, it is appropriate to implement the following tasks [1, 9]:

- forming the personality of the teacher and the student in the form of a person - a person - a person - individuality - a subject - a perfect person;
- effective use of trainings, business games, psychodrama and special exercises for the formation of certain qualities, traits, qualities, characteristics in students and teachers;
- improvement of teacher training methods, formation of creative research in them;
- application of other methods to increase efficiency of rating, test, module systems;
- sorting pedagogical technology tools according to the essence of science according to the age of students and discovering modern ones;
- to move away from narrative in texts and move to problematic, creative, independent thinking;
- creation and implementation of invariants and modifications of the educational program;
- to clearly implement interdisciplinary communication for the formation of educational motives without allowing repeated knowledge;
- use of active, innovative, non-traditional, creative methods and forms of the educational process;
- getting rid of formality about the structure and stages of the lesson, achieving interpersonal compatibility and equal rights by getting rid of obligation;
- turning the educational and training process (teacher and students and students' interaction) into a cooperative activity accelerates the decision-making of the practical expression of the "National Personnel Training Program" [2, 6].

One of the main criteria of technology is coherence, which is reflected in the main content of other criteria. Also, coherence in the content of pedagogical technology: coherence of processes; unity of goals and tasks; coherence of methods, forms and tools; expected results and future plans are created and implemented as a systematic process based on a holistic, coherent, step-by-step, manageable scientific idea.

The content of the concept of technology is revealed according to a certain field of human activity. For example, in production: mining of minerals, metal processing were also widely used, as well as book printing technologies [5].

Technologies in the educational process can be called "pedagogical technologies" and they can be included in the methodology, or vice versa, methodologies can be included in the pedagogical technologies.

For example: If the method of finding the greatest common divisor of two numbers (arithmetic, algebraic, Euclidean algorithm methods) is included in the technology of laboratory work in mathematics, then laboratory work is a component of a special method (methodology of teaching mathematics) [4].

There are also different views on how many stages and how pedagogical technologies can be implemented. For example, in the design of educational processes, it is possible to distinguish the following main tasks of the teacher in the entire educational process:

- 1) the task of ensuring the integrity of the educational process;
- 2) designing and implementing the educational process;
- 3) the task of self-analysis, that is, the teacher's analysis of his activity at different stages of this process.

Educational technology covers many operations consisting of three stages: design, implementation, control and evaluation.

Designing is the determination of the intended goal and the set of methods and means for its implementation. Within this block, operations are carried out in the following sequence: determining the time of implementation of educational technology (for the academic quarter, half-year, annual and entire educational period); analysis of educational materials; distinguishing goals and didactic tasks; bringing educational materials to a certain structure and distribution by time; determining the stages of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as the development of qualities and qualities of a person; Identifying methods and tools to engage students [7].

The implementation block is the process of implementing the goal set in the design-build block.

Control, the task of the control unit is to carry out current, intermediate and final controls in order to achieve the set goal, that is, to provide regular feedback and process information.

It is desirable to use individual-oriented pedagogical technologies in mathematics lessons. Person-centered mathematics teaching technology includes the following goals [3]:

- 1) to make every student interested in mathematics and ensure its development in the conditions of a cooperative environment;
- 2) development of students' creative abilities;
- 3) development of individual cognitive abilities of each child;
- 4) help a person to know himself, find his place, realize his potential.

The use of lesson projects based on pedagogical technologies in mathematics education: firstly, it opens the way to the use of various models in the educational process; secondly, inter-thematic and inter-subject coherence is ensured, thirdly, it serves as an important tool to ensure the coherence of theory and practice, fourthly, it helps to differentiate and individualize practical lessons; fifthly, an opportunity is created for students to work independently. Repetition and generalization of the topics covered not only helps students to form separate concepts, but also helps to understand the essence of a whole, integrated process, to perceive the unity of education. Each student is provided with an environment based on his/her personal characteristics.

Thus, in order to use the elements of pedagogical technology that ensure coherence in mathematics education, it is necessary to conduct a deep analysis of generalization and repetition lessons, to determine their content and the existing knowledge levels of students, to equip the classroom (auditorium) with technical tools, to provide the educational process with the necessary information and control work in advance planning is required.

ИҚТИБОСЛАР/СНОСКИ/REFERENCES

1. Dvoryatkina S., Shcherbatykh S., Shcherbatykh L. Synergy of mathematics, informatics and innovative didactics (on the example of retraining of teachers of mathematics) //ICERI2018 Proceedings. – IATED, 2018. – С. 2503-2509.
2. Galiakberova A. Innovative and information technologies in the educational process at the pedagogical university //SHS Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 97. – С. 01043.
3. Kakhkhorov S. K., Rasulova Z. D. Methodology of improving the professional activity of the future teacher of technology on the basis of modern educational technologies //Universal J. of Educational Research. – 2020. – Т. 8. – №. 12. – С. 7006-7014.
4. Osypova N. V., Tatochenko V. I. Improving the learning environment for future mathematics teachers with the use application of the dynamic mathematics system GeoGebra AR. – CEUR Workshop Proceedings, 2021.
5. Vlasova E. Z. et al. Effective adaptive training of students in Russian pedagogical universities to use e-learning technologies //Revista Espacios. – 2018. – Т. 39. – №. 23.
6. Абдуллаева Б.С. Фанлараро алоқадорликнинг методологик - дидактик асослари. (Ижтимоий-гуманитар йўналишдаги академик лицейларда математика ўқитиш мисолида): Пед. фан. доктори илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган дис. —Т.: ЎзПФТИ, 2006. — 264
7. Белобородова С.В. Зачем в школе изучают логарифмы // Математика в школе. — Москва, 2004. — №8. — С. 35-39.
8. Бершадская М.Д. и др. О преемственности образовательных программ разного уровня // Инновации в образовании. — Москва, 2002. — № 5 — С. 45-55.
9. Демин А. Ю. Информатика. Лабораторный практикум: учебное пособие для среднего профессионального образования / А. Ю. Демин, В. А. Дорофеев. — Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2019. — 133 с.

ISSN: 2181-4066
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4066

ПЕДАГОГИК ВА ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

I-ЖИЛД, 9-СОН

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-9

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-9

«Педагогик ва психологик тадқиқотлар» электрон журнали 2022 йил 22 декабрь куни № 054834-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

Эл. почта: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz